

MACHINE LEARNING FOR CREDIT ASSESSMENT IN MOBILE CREDIT AGGREGATORS

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Abstract

This paper investigates the application of machine learning (ML) techniques for credit assessment in mobile credit aggregators (MCA). Various ML algorithms such as logistic regression, decision trees, random forests, gradient boosting and neural networks are reviewed in terms of their applicability and accuracy in the context of mobile lending platforms. Real-world examples of the use of ML in such applications are analyzed. Challenges associated with the implementation of MO in modern MCA are discussed.

Keywords: machine learning (ML), credit assessment, credit scoring, mobile credit aggregators (MCA), logistic regression, artificial intelligence (AI).

Introduction

Modern financial technologies are actively transforming the lending market. One of the most notable advancements in this area is the development of mobile credit aggregators (MCA). These platforms provide users with convenient and fast access to credit offers from various financial institutions, significantly simplifying the loan acquisition process. However, as the number of clients and the volume of data processed increase, there arises a growing need for efficient and reliable methods of assessing clients' creditworthiness.

Machine learning (ML), as one of the crucial technologies in big data processing, offers a wide range of tools for analysis and prediction, making it indispensable in the automation of credit risk assessment. The application of ML algorithms can significantly enhance

the accuracy of forecasts, reduce decision-making time, and minimize the risks associated with lending to unreliable borrowers. The aim of this article is to analyze ML models for evaluating clients' creditworthiness within MCA.

Main part. Analysis of ML models

With the advancement of technology and the increasing volume of data, artificial intelligence (AI) and ML have become integral components of financial companies and mobile applications [1]. This is driven by the innovative approaches, flexibility, and scalability of such systems. Although the application of ML in various sectors began relatively recently, the adoption of these technologies has been growing steadily each year. It is projected that by 2024, the ML market will reach nearly \$80 billion (fig.1).

Figure 1. Projected size of the global ML market, billion USD [2]

The assessment of clients' creditworthiness is a critical element in the lending process, where decisions must be made quickly and accurately. When implementing ML models for credit assessment in MCA, various factors can be considered, such as annual income, loan term, education, age, occupation, and others [3]. To achieve this goal, different ML models are employed, each with its own characteristics.

Logistic regression is one of the simplest and most interpretable models for credit risk assessment. It is used to classify clients based on the probability of their creditworthiness [4]. The advantage of logistic regression lies in its ability to explain outcomes, which is

essential for understanding the factors that influence the likelihood of default. However, in the context of complex and multidimensional data, often encountered in mobile applications, logistic regression may show limited accuracy compared to more sophisticated models.

Gradient boosting, another ensemble method, outperforms many other models in accuracy due to its iterative improvement of each tree based on the errors of the previous one [5]. Algorithms such as XGBoost or LightGBM are frequently applied to credit scoring tasks due to their high efficiency and ability to handle large datasets. They provide more accurate predictions

compared to single decision trees or logistic regression, making them preferable for use in mobile applications.

Neural networks, especially deep ones, demonstrate high accuracy in predictive tasks, including creditworthiness assessment. They can capture complex and multidimensional dependencies in data, making them particularly useful when dealing with a large number of features and unstructured data, such as text or behavioral patterns. The main drawback of neural networks is their low interpretability, which can pose challenges when explaining results to users or regulatory bodies.

The **Support Vector Machine (SVM)** method is used for classification with a high level of accuracy, especially in tasks with well-defined boundaries between classes. SVM performs well in high-dimensional data tasks, although it may be less efficient on large datasets due to its computational intensity. This method can be applied in mobile applications for specific credit scoring tasks requiring high precision.

Decision trees provide a more flexible approach to modeling, allowing for the consideration of nonlinear relationships between features. The model is easily interpretable, and its visualization enables the explanation of decisions to users. **Random forests**, as an ensemble method consisting of multiple decision trees, enhance the stability and accuracy of predictions, reducing the likelihood of overfitting. These models are widely used in MCA due to their ability to process complex and diverse data.

In scientific studies conducted in 2024, the predictive capability of modern ML models in the financial sector was examined [6]. Metrics such as accuracy, F1-score (calculated from the confusion matrix), and area under the curve (AUC) were included in the analysis. It was found that the random forest model outperformed other methods across all performance evaluation metrics (table 1).

Table 1.

Prediction results and model accuracy

Models	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC	Rank
Linear discriminant analysis	70.9%	0.79	0.464	4
Logistic regression	75.8%	0.822	0.533	2
Decision trees	64.3%	0.738	0.575	5
Random forest	78.2%	0.833	0.715	1
SVM	74.8%	0.81	0.563	3

For the same purpose of assessing the predictive capability of the proposed algorithms, the F1 score confirms the ability of the random forest to accurately identify reliable clients and distinguish them from unfavorable ones. The application of advanced ML models and algorithms enables achieving high prediction accuracy, which can positively impact user satisfaction and enhance competitiveness in the financial market.

Analysis of ML implementation in MCA and evaluation of the challenges of such innovations

Modern financial companies actively utilize ML methods to enhance the processes of assessing clients' creditworthiness. The application of such approaches allows for the automation and significant acceleration of decision-making processes, providing more accurate and personalized credit offers.

The AI-based fintech platform **Upstart** employs complex ML models for evaluating clients' creditworthiness, offering more equitable loan terms. Upstart's algorithms consider a wide range of factors, such as education, employment, and credit history, to create a more accurate credit profile. These models are trained on large datasets, including millions of transactions and historical records. According to the company, this approach has reduced the number of defaults and increased transaction volumes [7].

One of the largest peer-to-peer lending platforms, **Lending Club**, actively uses ML to assess borrowers' creditworthiness [8]. Their ML models analyze thousands of data points about clients, including their financial history, behavior, and other demographic factors throughout the client's lifecycle. This approach allows the company to expand access to credit while ensuring

high returns for credit investors, taking risk into account.

A leading company in the «buy now, pay later» sector, **Affirm**, also uses ML to assess clients' creditworthiness in real time. More detailed and complex models can account for different variables and their interactions, allowing Affirm to approve loans for a broader range of borrowers. By using advanced ML algorithms and automating processes, Affirm can make lending decisions almost instantly and process a large volume of applications without compromising risk assessment accuracy [9].

The analysis of real-world examples shows that the introduction of ML into mobile credit platforms opens up new opportunities for risk analysis, minimizing defaults, and increasing the accessibility of credit services to a wider audience. As ML continues to develop, decision-making practices based on it will gradually increase through automation and process accuracy.

However, the implementation of AI and ML technologies may also be associated with several limitations that need to be considered when developing and applying such systems. One of these challenges is the **insufficiency and heterogeneity** of data, which can complicate its integration and analysis. This may be due to various factors, such as the absence of a credit history or the diversity of information provided from different sources.

Many modern ML algorithms, such as deep neural networks, are difficult to interpret due to their «**black box**» models [10]. This creates challenges for lenders when explaining the reasons for credit denial to clients

or regulators. The lack of transparency in decisions made by ML models can lead to reduced trust and increased regulatory risks.

Training and deploying complex ML models require **significant computational resources**. With the growing number of users and data volumes, this can lead to high infrastructure costs [11]. ML models trained on historical data may also respond incorrectly to sudden changes in economic or market conditions. This can result in inaccurate forecasts and increased risks for lenders.

Overcoming these challenges requires a comprehensive approach, including improving data quality, developing more interpretable models, and optimizing computational processes [12]. Successfully addressing these issues will enable more effective use of ML for creditworthiness assessment in MCA, ensuring more accurate and fair outcomes.

Conclusions

The application of ML in MCA represents a powerful tool for transforming traditional methods of creditworthiness assessment. Such approaches enable improvements in prediction accuracy, personalization of credit offers, and expansion of access to financial services. The use of modern technologies and the adaptation of ML provide companies with significant competitive advantages. The implementation of logistic regression, decision trees, and random forests models helps deploy precise and automated predictive solutions based on various client data.

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